

CERTAINTY UMANCHESTER's DMP

Version 0

Description

The Data Management Plan (DMP) for data created at the UNIMAN is developed in the context of effectively managing and preserving valuable data generated for CERTAINTY project.

The DMP for UNIMAN data is designed to maximize the value, accessibility, and impact of the data produced, supporting the Institute's mission in advancing meteorological research and services.

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Grant

CERTAINTY

Researchers

Harri Kokkola (orcid:0000-0002-1404-6670), Paul Connolly (orcid:0000-0002-3294-7405), Hugh Coe

Organizations

Finnish Meteorological Institute, University of Manchester

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [CERTAINTY UMANCHESTER's DMP](#)

Description:

The Data Management Plan (DMP) for data created at the UNIMAN is developed in the context of effectively managing and preserving valuable data generated for CERTAINTY project.

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[Harri Kokkola \(orcid:0000-0002-1404-6670\)](#)

[Paul Connolly \(orcid:0000-0002-3294-7405\)](#)

[Hugh Coe](#)

Organizations:

[Finnish Meteorological Institute](#)

[University of Manchester](#)

Contact: [Anca Hienola](#)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [European Commission](#)||[EC](#)

Grants: [CERTAINTY](#)

Project: [CERTAINTY](#)

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

FAAM aircraft aerosol and cloud data

UK FAAM aircraft data collected during a number of missions across different regions and cloud types:

1. In-cloud droplet size distributions and ice size distributions and habits.
2. Aerosol physical and chemical properties
3. meteorological, physical state and aircraft data

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

The data were originally collected during previous campaign from different funders. They are publicly available and will be re-worked for wider use within CERTAINTY

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

The observational data have been processed to ensure that they can be used by a wider range of users

1.1.5 What is its format?

netcdf

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

tens of GB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To improve a product
- To combine with other data

The data will be used to identify different properties of different clouds under different scenarios. They will be used to inform models

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Data were originally collected using the FAAM aircraft. The data have been quality assured, metadata is supplied and are available publicly through the UK CEDa data portal

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

This will be principally of use to researchers wishing to understand the detailed microphysical properties of different cloud types under different conditions

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers

DOI

ORCID

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

NetCDF Attribute Convention for Dataset Discovery

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

No

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

CEDA

<https://archive.ceda.ac.uk/>

The CEDA Archive forms part of NERC's Environmental Data Service (EDS) and is responsible for looking after data from atmospheric and earth observation research.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

Has certification

3.2.1.3 Add certification(s)

CoreTrustSeal

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

download from CEDA or available through UNIMAN

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

always

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Data conform to format specification

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Storage

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of national infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Hugh Coe

5.1 Data Security

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

Data access

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

more than 20 years

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

University of Manchester Laboratory Data on Secondary Ice Mechanisms

Data gathered to quantify secondary ice production by the freezing of raindrops during collisions with existing ice crystals. This dataset will consist of:

1. Video analysis of individual collisions between drops and ice crystals and the resulting fragments
2. Metadata quantifying the experimental conditions

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

This will be new data collected during experiments funded by the Horizon Europe program, CERTAINTY.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Experimental

Processed videos of individual droplet and ice particle interactions filmed in the laboratory. The videos will discriminate the ice phase from droplets. Different droplet sizes and ice crystal sizes will be used as this is a key parameter we are

investigating. Different temperatures / environmental conditions will also be used.

1.1.5 What is its format?

Videos will be stored in MP4 format. Figures will be stored in PDF format or other image formats (e.g. PNG or JPG).

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

tens of gigabytes

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To keep on record

These videos will be used to develop a parameterisation that describes how many secondary ice crystals are generated when droplets of different sizes collide with ice crystals. The parameterisation will depend on temperature and perhaps relative humidity (to be determined).

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The data will be taken in the Manchester Ice Cloud Chamber laboratories at the University of Manchester, UK. The setting for the experiment is a purpose built container where we can collide supercooled drops and ice crystals, and film the results with polarised light and filters to discriminate ice. A pilot study has taken place <https://acp.copernicus.org/articles/21/18519/2021/> and the data were stored using Figshare at the University of Manchester. https://figshare.manchester.ac.uk/collections/Secondary_ice_production_during_the_break-up_of_freezing_water_drops_on_impact_with_ice_particles/5476557

Figshare is a FAIR-aligned (findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable) data repository service at the University of Manchester

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers

- Research communities
- Education

SIP parameterisation can have an extremely large effect on the representation of clouds in numerical models. As such we need to allow proper scrutiny of any developed parameterisation. For this reason we need to share the data that are used to create a parameterisation. We expect that groups at the Met Office, and Universities working in the area of mixed-phase clouds will be interested in viewing this data to input into parameterisation development. We also expect that researchers in the CERTAINTY project will be able to use the resource and provide further input into its development, sharing ideas throughout the project.

We also envisage using the videos in education. Prof. Connolly teaches courses in Environmental Modelling and Measuring and Predicting to both Undergraduates and Postgraduate students. He teaches about the importance of cloud microphysics on quantities such as radiative transfer and precipitation on the ground. He will use these videos as teaching material. Prof. Connolly and other academics at the University of Manchester also visit schools and colleges to give talks on outreach. This data will also provide visual examples of processes in action to this community.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers
- Organizations identifiers
- National identifiers

DOI

ORCID

Crossref

We plan to use Figshare, which is supported by the University of Manchester
<https://www.library.manchester.ac.uk/services/research/open-research/data/>

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

NetCDF Attribute Convention for Dataset Discovery

This has not been fully decided, but we could use NetCDF to explain the data.

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Reference

The conditions in the experiments will be reported along with each record.

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

No

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

No

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

University of Manchester figshare

<https://www.library.manchester.ac.uk/services/research/open-research/data/>

The University of Manchester is a public research university in Manchester, England. The main campus is south of Manchester City Centre on Oxford Road. The university owns and operates major cultural assets such as the Manchester Museum, The Whitworth art gallery, the John Rylands Library, the Tabley House Collection and the Jodrell Bank Observatory – a UNESCO World Heritage Site. The University of Manchester is considered a red brick university, a product of the civic university movement of the late 19th century. The current University of Manchester was formed in 2004 following the merger of the University of Manchester Institute of Science and Technology (UMIST) and the Victoria University of Manchester. This followed a century of the two institutions working closely with one another.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Supports retention

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

N/A

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Unknown

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Secondary ice production during the break-up of freezing water drops on impact with ice particles

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

indefinite

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

No

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.4 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Analyses
- Variable definitions

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Data conform to format specification
- Consistency verified with data models and standards

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use

Direct cost

It is currently free at the point of use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

- Use of institution infrastructure
- Collaboration with other Projects

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Not appointed

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

Data storage

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

We will store on Figshare and local servers. if this becomes non persistent we will store on Zenodo and potentially Github.

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

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